

Enhanced Light-GBM Model using Borderline-SMOTE and Modified Bayesian Optimization for Early Detection of Fetal Health Classification

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX A: BORDERLINE-SMOTE ALGORITHM AND MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

This appendix presents the algorithmic steps and mathematical formulation of the Borderline-SMOTE technique used in this study to address class imbalance.

Let x_i be a minority class sample, and let $x_{i,j}$ denote one of its k -nearest neighbors belonging to the same class. A synthetic sample x_{new} is calculated as shown in (9).

$$x_{new} = x_i + \lambda * (x_{i,j} - x_i), \lambda \sim U(0,1) \quad (9)$$

A sample x_i is considered a borderline instance if more than half of its k -nearest neighbors belong to the majority class. The pseudo code steps of the Borderline-SMOTE algorithm is described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Borderline-SMOTE

1. Input:

$X_{minority}$: set of minority class,

k : number of neighbors,

α : oversampling ratio

2. Output:

S : Set of synthetic minority samples

3. Initialize synthetic samples list $S = []$.

4. **for** each sample $x_i \in X_{minority}$ **do**

5. Find k nearest neighbors of x_i from the full dataset.

6. Count the number of majority class neighbors $N_{majority}$

7. **if** $N_{majority} \geq \frac{k}{2}$ **then**

8. add x_i to the borderline samples B .

9. **end if**

10. **end for**

11. **for** each borderline sample $x_i \in B$ **do**

12. Find k -nearest neighbors of x_i from $X_{minority}$.

13. **for** each neighbor of x_i **do**

14. Generate x_{new} using $x_{new} = x_i + \lambda * (x_{i,j} - x_i), \lambda \sim U(0,1)$

15. Add x_{new} to S .

16. **and for**

17. **and for**

18. **Return** $X_{minority} \cup S$.

APPENDIX B: LIGHTGBM TRAINING ALGORITHM

Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) is a decision-tree-based ensemble framework that uses gradient boosting to improve classification and regression tasks. Its core innovation lies in the leaf-wise tree growth strategy, which chooses the leaf with the maximum loss reduction for expansion rather than growing the tree level-by-level. This strategy, combined with Gradient-based One-Sided Sampling (GOSS) and Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB), allows LightGBM to achieve high accuracy with reduced training time, especially on large datasets [4], [7], [8].

Let $X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ represent the training dataset with N samples and M features, and let Y be the corresponding target values. The objective of LightGBM is to minimize a regularized loss function as shown in (10).

$$L(f) = \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i - f(x_i)]^2 + \Omega(f) \quad (10)$$

where $\Omega(f)$ is a regularization term that controls model complexity to mitigate overfitting.

During each iteration, LightGBM employs an additive training strategy in which a new tree $h_t(x)$ is added to correct the residuals of the previous ensemble $f_{t-1}(x)$, as described in (11).

$$h_t(x) = \arg \min_h \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i - f_{t-1}(x_i)]^2 + \Omega(h) \quad (11)$$

To construct each tree efficiently, LightGBM computes the negative gradient (also referred to as the pseudo-residual) of the loss function, as expressed in (12).

$$g_i = -\frac{\partial L(f_{t-1}(x_i))}{\partial f_{t-1}(x_i)} \quad (12)$$

Using the GOSS technique, a subset S_t of training examples is selected, emphasizing those with large gradient values. This subset is used to train a new decision tree, which is grown in a leaf-wise manner, selecting splits that offer the greatest loss reduction rather than expanding all leaves evenly (as in level-wise methods). This strategy enables deeper trees and captures complex data structures more effectively. The final classification is made by aggregating the outputs of all trees in the ensemble, as shown in (13).

$$f(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T w_t h_t(x) \quad (13)$$

where T is the total number of trees, $h_t(x)$ is the output of the t -th tree, and w_t denotes its weight, determined by the boosting process based on its contribution to minimizing the overall loss.

The training procedure for LightGBM is described in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: LightGBM Training Procedure

1. **Input:** Training data (X, Y) , learning rate η , number of iterations T
 2. **Output:** Final prediction function $f_T(x)$
 3. Initialize $f_0(x) = \text{log-odds or mean of } Y$
 4. **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
 5. Compute gradients g_i and Hessians h_i for each sample
 6. Use GOSS to sample informative instances
 7. Apply EFB to reduce dimensionality
 8. Train tree $h_t(x)$ using leaf-wise growth strategy
 9. Update prediction: $f_t(x) = f_{t-1}(x) + \eta * h_t(x)$
 10. **end for**
 11. **Return** final model $f_T(x)$
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APPENDIX C: BAYESIAN OPTIMIZATION AND TREE-STRUCTURED PARZEN ESTIMATOR

1. Bayesian Optimization

Bayesian Optimization is a global optimization technique that constructs a surrogate model to approximate the objective function and uses an acquisition function to propose promising sampling points. It is particularly effective for optimizing machine learning hyperparameters. The main steps of BO are described below:

1. Initialization: Evaluate the objective function $f(x)$ at n initial points as shown in (14).

$$D = \{(x_1, f(x_1)), (x_2, f(x_2)), \dots, (x_n, f(x_n))\} \quad (14)$$

2. Surrogate Model Construction: A Gaussian Process (GP) is used to model the objective function, as shown in (15).

$$f(x) \sim GP(m(x), k(x, x')) \quad (15)$$

where $m(x)$ is the mean function and $k(x, x')$ is the kernel function, often chosen as the Radial Basis Function (RBF), as shown in (16).

$$k(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (16)$$

3. Optimisation of the acquisition function: An Expected Improvement (EI) is used to select the next point, as shown in (17).

$$EI(x) = \mathbb{E}[\max(0, f(x^+) - f(x))] \quad (17)$$

where, $f(x^+)$ is the best value observed so far.

4. Evaluation and Update: Evaluate $f(x_t)$ update the dataset $D = D \cup \{x_t, f(x_t)\}$ refine the surrogate model.

The pseudo code steps of the BO algorithm is described in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3: Bayesian Optimization (BO)

1. Initialization: N population size; T maximum iteration; dataset $D = \{\}$
 2. Evaluate $f(x)$ at N random points and add to D .
 3. Set $t = 1$
 4. **while** $t \leq T$ **do**
 5. Fit Gaussian Process to observed data D .
 6. Select next point x_t by optimizing acquisition function $EI(x)$ using (4).
 7. Evaluate $f(x_t)$.
 8. Update dataset $D = D \cup \{x_t, f(x_t)\}$.
 9. Update Gaussian Process model with new data.
 10. Set $t = t + 1$
 11. **end while**
 12. **Return** best hyperparameters found.
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2. Tree-structured Parzen Estimator

The Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) is a more efficient alternative to traditional BO. It overcomes the computational limitations of BO by partitioning the data into two groups based on the values of the objective function and modelling the probability distribution using kernel density estimation (KDE) [2]. The main steps of TPE are described below:

1. **Initialization:** The process starts by evaluating the objective function $f(x)$ at several random points to build an initial dataset $D = \{(x_1, f(x_1)), (x_2, f(x_2)), \dots, (x_n, f(x_n))\}$.
2. **Data Splitting:** The dataset is divided into two groups based on the objective function values: the good group ($y < y^*$) and the bad group ($y \geq y^*$). The threshold y^* is calculated as the γ -th percentile of the objective function values, where γ is a predefined parameter.
3. **Distribution Modeling:** The probability distribution of the hyperparameters is modeled using KDE for both groups, as shown in (18).

$$p(x|y) = \begin{cases} l(x) & \text{if } y < y^* \\ g(x) & \text{if } y \geq y^* \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Here, $l(x)$ represents the distribution for hyperparameters yielding good values, and $g(x)$ represents the distribution for hyperparameters yielding bad values.

4. **Next Point Selection:** The next point is selected by maximizing the ratio $\frac{l(x)}{g(x)}$. This ensures that the algorithm focuses on regions likely to yield better results.
5. **Evaluation and Update:** The objective function is evaluated at the selected point x_t , yielding $f(x_t)$. The dataset is updated by adding the new observation, as shown in (19).

$$D = D \cup \{(x_t, f(x_t))\} \quad (19)$$

6. **Iteration:** Steps 2-5 are repeated until a convergence criterion is met or the maximum number of iterations is reached. The pseudocode steps of the TPE algorithm are described in Algorithm 4.
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Algorithm 4: Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE)

1. **Initialization:** N population size; T maximum iteration; dataset $D = \{\}$; γ percentile
2. Evaluate $f(x)$ at N random points and add to D .
3. Set $t = 1$
4. **while** $t \leq T$ **do**
5. Calculate threshold y^* as the γ -th percentile of $f(x)$ values in D .
6. Split D into good $y < y^*$ and bad $y \geq y^*$ groups.

7. Fit KDE to good and bad groups to model $l(x)$ and $g(x)$ using (5).
 8. Select next point x_t by maximizing $\frac{l(x)}{g(x)}$.
 9. Evaluate $f(x_t)$.
 10. Update dataset use Equation (5).
 11. Set $t = t + 1$
 12. **end while**
 13. **Return** best hyperparameters found.
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